

Supplementary Table S6. Literature records of predation and probable predation on stromboids, collated from published field observation records (see reference list below table), here listed with stromboid family and species, predator, size of stromboid, ontogenetic stage, relevant comments, and literature reference(s).

Family	Species	Predator	Size of stromboid (mm)	Stage	Mode of predation	Reference
Strombidae	<i>Aliger gigas</i>	<i>Octopus vulgaris</i>	110	Juvenile	Likely predation by cutting off the oxygen supply or by a discharge of salivary gland toxin (see MacGinitie and MacGinitie, 1949). Octopuses are known to drill molluscs; however, no drilling site was noted.	Randall, 1964
Strombidae	<i>Aliger gigas</i>	Octopus	—	—	Crushing of shell by an octopus (presumed killing)	Randall, 1964
Strombidae	<i>Aliger gigas</i>	Crab	127— 190	Juvenile	Crushing of shell; invert shell and insertion of chelae into aperture. NB: Randall (1964) suggested hermit crab (<i>Petrochirus diogenes</i>) as the predator, but more likely predators are the box crabs (<i>Calappa</i> sp.) that are common on the plain (Berg, 1974).	Randall, 1964; Berg, 1974
Strombidae	<i>Aliger gigas</i> ; <i>Aliger costatus</i>	Spiny lobsters (<i>Panulirus argus</i>)	<i>A. gigas</i> : 41-54 and 108	<i>A. gigas</i> : Juvenile	Crush, peel or chipping away with mandibles, or a combination	Randall, 1964; Delgado, 2002
Strombidae	<i>Aliger gigas</i>	Tiger shark (<i>Galeocerdo cuvieri</i>)	—	Juvenile/ subadult	Ingestion; conch found whole in stomach	Randall, 1964
Strombidae	<i>Aliger gigas</i>	Spotted eagle ray (<i>Aetobatis narinari</i>)	ca. 100- 135	Juvenile	Crushing of shell (and possible removal of operculum using jaws)	Randall, 1964
Strombidae	<i>Aliger gigas</i>	Southern stingray (<i>Dasyatis americana</i>)	—	—	Possible crushing of shell, or invert shell and tear foot when the foot was trying to tip shell back over.	Randall, 1964; Stoner, 1994
Strombidae	<i>Terestrombus fragilis</i>	Goatfish	—	—	Diver observation: a goatfish was trying to feed on it	Wieneke et al., 2022
Strombidae	<i>Aliger gigas</i>	Hogfish (<i>Lachnolaimus maximus</i>)	—	Juvenile	Crushing of shell	Randall, 1964

Strombidae	<i>Aliger gigas</i>	Porcupinefish (<i>Diodon hystrix</i>)	15-16	Juvenile	Crushing of shell	Randall, 1964
Strombidae	<i>Conomurex persicus</i>	Pearly razorfish (<i>Xyrichtys novacula</i>)	—	—	Probably crushing (see Beltrano et al., 2006)	Üstüner et al., 2018
Strombidae	<i>Aliger gigas</i>	Permit fish (<i>Trachinotus falcatus</i>)	—	—	Known to crush molluscs	Randall, 1964
Strombidae	<i>Aliger gigas</i>	Queen triggerfish (<i>Balistes vetula</i>)	—	—	Known to crush molluscs	Randall, 1964
Strombidae	<i>Aliger gigas</i>	Loggerhead turtle (<i>Caretta caretta</i>)	Some parts of shell 15 mm thick	Adult	Crushing of shell	Randall, 1964; Iversen et al., 1986
Strombidae	<i>Aliger gigas</i>	Dolphin (<i>Tursiops truncatus</i>)	—	—	Randall (1964) considered it likely the animal wrenches off part of the foot of a conch with its jaws	Randall, 1964
Strombidae	<i>Aliger gigas</i> ; <i>Aliger costatus</i>	Tulip snail (<i>Fasciolaria tulipa</i>)	<i>A. gigas</i> : 150	<i>A. gigas</i> : Juvenile	Diver observation: <i>Aliger costatus</i>	Randall, 1964; Wieneke et al., 2022
Strombidae	<i>Aliger gigas</i>	Florida horse conch (<i>Pleuroploca gigantea</i>)	—	—	—	Randall, 1964
Strombidae	<i>Aliger costatus</i> ; <i>Lobatus raninus</i>	Apple murex (<i>Murex pomum</i>)	—	—	—	Robertson 1961; Randall, 1964
Strombidae	<i>Maculastrombus mutabilis</i> ; <i>Maculastrombus maculatus</i> ; <i>Gibberulus gibberulus</i> ; <i>Conomurex luhuanus</i> ; <i>Lentigo lentiginosus</i> ; <i>Lambis scorpius</i> ; <i>Lambis lambis</i> ; <i>Harpago chiragra</i> , <i>Lambis truncata</i> ; <i>Tridentarius dentatus</i>	Cone snail <i>Conus</i> – also for some, <i>Nassa</i> , and <i>Cymatium</i>	—	<i>T. dentatus</i> : Juvenile	Escape response is triggered by these predatory snails; however, there is currently no evidence that cones eat strombids in their natural habitat. Gut and faecal pellet analyses have also not revealed conch snail remains within cone snails.	Berg et al., 1974
Aporrhaidae	<i>Aporrhais pespelecani</i>	<i>Octopus vulgaris</i>	—	—	In laboratory (prey/predator caught in same locality): holes drilled in opercular surface of the spire / opercular region	Nixon and Macconachie, 1988

Aporrhaidae	<i>Arrhoges occidentalis</i>	Crab (presumed)	—	—	Chipped outer lip of shell in similar manner to that observed in the lab by Vermeij (1976). Some shells had been weakened by infestations of boring polychaete <i>Polydora commensalis</i>	Perron, 1978
Aporrhaidae	<i>Arrhoges occidentalis</i>	Fish or crab – possibly wolf fish <i>Anarhichas lupus</i> or crab <i>Cancer irroratus</i> (presumed)	—	—	Crushed	Perron, 1978
Aporrhaidae	<i>Arrhoges occidentalis</i>	Predatory gastropod – possibly <i>Colus stimpsoni</i> (presumed)	—	—	No damage to shell	Perron, 1978
Struthiolariidae	<i>Pellicaria vermis</i>	Eagle ray (<i>Holorhinus tenuicaudatus</i>)	—	—	Stomach contents	Godfriaux, 1969
Struthiolariidae	<i>Pellicaria vermis</i>	Snapper (<i>Chrysophrys auratus</i>)	—	—	Stomach contents. Comprises tiny portion of diet – so maybe scavenged	Godfriaux, 1969
Struthiolariidae	<i>Pellicaria vermis</i> ; <i>Struthiolaria papulosa</i>	Rig shark (<i>Mustelus lenticulatus</i>)	—	—	Stomach contents	King and Clark, 1984
Struthiolariidae	<i>Struthiolaria papulosa</i>	Starfish (<i>Sclerasterias mollis</i>)	—	—	Displays escape response in presence of starfish but predator hasn't been observed to feed on the snail in aquarium tanks. Occurs in same habitat	Crump, 1968
Struthiolariidae	<i>Struthiolaria papulosa</i>	Possibly rays	—	—	Crushing	Beu, 2012

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